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Information Technology (IJCSIT)**

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i10-index	218	166

ISSN: 0975-3826(online); 0975-4660 (Print)

<http://airccse.org/journal/ijsit.html>

SECURITY THREATS ON CLOUD COMPUTING VULNERABILITIES

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ABSTRACT

Clouds provide a powerful computing platform that enables individuals and organizations to perform variety levels of tasks such as: use of online storage space, adoption of business applications, development of customized computer software, and creation of a “realistic” network environment. In previous years, the number of people using cloud services has dramatically increased and lots of data has been stored in cloud computing environments. In the meantime, data breaches to cloud services are also increasing every year due to hackers who are always trying to exploit the security vulnerabilities of the architecture of cloud. In this paper, three cloud service models were compared; cloud security risks and threats were investigated based on the nature of the cloud service models. Real world cloud attacks were included to demonstrate the techniques that hackers used against cloud computing systems. In addition, countermeasures to cloud security breaches are presented.

KEYWORDS

Cloud computing, cloud security threats and countermeasures, cloud service models

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/jcsit/5313ijcsit06.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit2013_curr.html

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DATA WAREHOUSE AND BIG DATA INTEGRATION

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ABSTRACT

Big Data triggered furthered an influx of research and prospective on concepts and processes pertaining previously to the Data Warehouse field. Some conclude that Data Warehouse as such will disappear; others present Big Data as the natural Data Warehouse evolution (perhaps without identifying a clear division between the two); and finally, some others pose a future of convergence, partially exploring the possible integration of both. In this paper, we revise the underlying technological features of Big Data and Data Warehouse, highlighting their differences and areas of convergence. Even when some differences exist, both technologies could (and should) be integrated because they both aim at the same purpose: data exploration and decision making support. We explore some convergence strategies, based on the common elements in both technologies. We present a revision of the state-of-the-art in integration proposals from the point of view of the purpose, methodology, architecture and underlying technology, highlighting the common elements that support both technologies that may serve as a starting point for full integration and we propose a proposal of integration between the two technologies.

KEYWORDS

Big Data, Data Warehouse, Integration, Hadoop, NoSql, MapReduce, 7V's, 3C's, M&G

For More Details : <https://airconline.com/ijsit/V9N2/9217ijsit01.pdf>

Volume Link : http://aircse.org/journal/ijsit2017_curr.html

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DATA MINING MODEL PERFORMANCE OF SALES PREDICTIVE ALGORITHMS BASED ON RAPIDMINER WORKFLOWS

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ABSTRACT

By applying RapidMiner workflows has been processed a dataset originated from different data files, and containing information about the sales over three years of a large chain of retail stores. Subsequently, has been constructed a Deep Learning model performing a predictive algorithm suitable for sales forecasting. This model is based on artificial neural network –ANN- algorithm able to learn the model starting from sales historical data and by pre-processing the data. The best built model uses a multilayer neural network together with an “optimized operator” able to find automatically the best parameter setting of the implemented algorithm. In order to prove the best performing predictive model, other machine learning algorithms have been tested. The performance comparison has been performed between Support Vector Machine –SVM-, k-Nearest Neighbor k-NN-, Gradient Boosted Trees, Decision Trees, and Deep Learning algorithms. The comparison of the degree of correlation between real and predicted values, the average absolute error and the relative average error proved that ANN exhibited the best performance. The Gradient Boosted Trees approach represents an alternative approach having the second best performance. The case of study has been developed within the framework of an industry project oriented on the integration of high performance data mining models able to predict sales using –ERP- and customer relationship management –CRM- tools.

KEYWORDS

RapidMiner, Neural Network, Deep Learning, Gradient Boosted Trees, Data Mining Performance, Sales Prediction.

For More Details : <http://aircconline.com/ijcsit/V10N3/10318ijcsit03.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit2018_curr.html

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A WIRELESS NETWORK INFRASTRUCTURE ARCHITECTURE FOR RURAL COMMUNITIES

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ABSTRACT

Wireless network implementation is a viable option for building network infrastructure in rural communities. Rural people lack network infrastructures for information services and socio-economic development. The aim of this study was to develop a wireless network infrastructure architecture for network services to rural dwellers. A user-centered approach was applied in the study and a wireless network infrastructure was designed and deployed to cover five rural locations. Data was collected and analyzed to assess the performance of the network facilities. The results shows that the system had been performing adequately without any downtime with an average of 200 users per month and the quality of service has remained high. The transmit/receive rate of 300Mbps was thrice as fast as the normal Ethernet transmit/receive specification with an average throughput of 1 Mbps. The multiple output/multiple input(MIMO) point-to-multipoint network design increased the network throughput and the quality of service experienced by the users

KEYWORDS

Wifi-based Rural Extension, Wireless Fidelity(WiFi), Rural Community, Internet, Network Architecture.

For More Details : <http://airconline.com/ijsit/V9N3/9317ijsit04.pdf>

Volume Link : http://aircse.org/journal/ijsit2017_curr.html

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AGILE DISTRIBUTED SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT IN NINE CENTRAL EUROPEAN TEAMS: CHALLENGES, BENEFITS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Although initially designed for co-located teams, agile methodologies promise mitigation to the challenges present in distributed software development with their demand for frequent communication. We examine the application of agile practices in software engineering teams with low geographical distribution in Austria and Germany. To gather insights on challenges and benefits faced by distributed teams we conduct interviews with eleven representatives and analyse the interview transcripts using the inductive category formation method. As a result, we identify four major challenges, such as technical obstructions or the impediments different language abilities have on communication, and four benefits, regarding collaboration and information radiation, that agile methods yield in distributed teams. Based on our analysis of challenges and benefits, we deduct seven recommendations to improve collaboration, overcome distance and avoid pitfalls. Key recommendations for teams with low geographical distance include that teams should get together at certain points to build relationships and trust and share information face-to-face.

KEYWORDS

Agile Distributed Software Development, Distributed Agile, Nearshoring, Agile Methods

For More Details : <http://airconline.com/ijcsit/V11N1/11119ijcsit01.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit2019_curr.html

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FUTURE AND CHALLENGES OF INTERNET OF THINGS

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ABSTRACT

The world is moving forward at a fast pace, and the credit goes to ever growing technology. One such concept is IOT (Internet of things) with which automation is no longer a virtual reality. IOT connects various non-living objects through the internet and enables them to share information with their community network to automate processes for humans and makes their lives easier. The paper presents the future challenges of IoT , such as the technical (connectivity , compatibility and longevity , standards , intelligent analysis and actions , security), business (investment , modest revenue model etc.), societal (changing demands , new devices, expense, customer confidence etc.) and legal challenges (laws, regulations, procedures, policies etc.). A section also discusses the various myths that might hamper the progress of IOT, security of data being the most critical factor of all. An optimistic approach to people in adopting the unfolding changes brought by IOT will also help in its growth

KEYWORDS

IoT, Internet of Things, Security, Sensors

For More Details : <https://aireconline.com/ticsit/V10N2/10218ijcsit02.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit2018_curr.html

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AN EXPLORATION OF THE FACTORS AFFECTING USERS' SATISFACTION WITH MOBILE PAYMENTS

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ABSTRACT

Mobile payment allows consumers to make more flexible payments through convenient mobile devices. While mobile payment is easy and time save, the operation and security of mobile payment must ensure that the payment is fast, convenient, reliable and safety in order to increase the users' satisfaction. Therefore, this study based on technology acceptance model to explore the impact of external variables through perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use on users' satisfaction. The data analysis methods used in this study are descriptive statistical analysis, reliability and validity analysis, Pearson correlation analysis and regression analysis to verify the hypotheses. The results show that all hypotheses are supported. However, mobile payment is still subject to many restrictions on development and there are limited related researches. The results of this study provided insight into the factors that affect the users' satisfaction for mobile payment. Related services development of mobile payment and future research suggestions are also offered.

KEYWORDS

Mobile Payment, Technology Acceptance Model, Users' satisfaction

For More Details : <https://airconline.com/ijsit/V9N3/9317ijsit08.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/ijsit2017_curr.html

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BIG DATA IN CLOUD COMPUTING REVIEW AND OPPORTUNITIES

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ABSTRACT

Big Data is used in decision making process to gain useful insights hidden in the data for business and engineering. At the same time it presents challenges in processing, cloud computing has helped in advancement of big data by providing computational, networking and storage capacity. This paper presents the review, opportunities and challenges of transforming big data using cloud computing resources.

KEYWORDS

Big data; cloud computing; analytics; database; data warehouse

For More Details : <https://airconline.com/ijsit/V11N4/11419ijsit04.pdf>

Volume Link : http://aircse.org/journal/ijsit2019_curr.html

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PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF LTE NETWORK USING MAXIMUM FLOW ALGORITHM

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we propose a new traffic flow model of the Long Term Evaluation (LTE) network for the Evolved Universal Terrestrial Radio Access Network (E-UTRAN). Here only one Evolve Node B (eNB) nearest to the Mobility Management Entity (MME) and Serving Gateway (S-GW) will use the S1 link to bridge the E-UTRAN and Evolved Packet Core (EPC). All the eNBs of a tracking area will be connected to each other by the X2 link. Determination of capacity of a links of such a network is a challenging job since each node offers its own traffic and at the same time conveys traffic of other nodes. In this paper, we apply maximum flow algorithm including superposition theorem to solve the traffic flow of radio network. Using the total flow per subcarrier, a new traffic model is also developed in the paper. The relation among the traffic parameters: 'blocking probability', 'offered traffic', 'instantaneous capacity', 'average holding time', and 'number of users' are shown graphically under both QPSK and 16-QAM. The concept of the network will be helpful to improve the SINR of the received signal of eNBs located long distance relative to MME/S-GW.

KEYWORDS

Aggregate offered traffic, blocking probability, traffic channel, weighted graph and RB.

For More Details : <http://airconline.com/ijcsit/V12N4/12420ijcsit06.pdf>

Volume Link : http://aircse.org/journal/ijcsit2020_curr.html

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CLUSTERING ALGORITHM FOR A HEALTHCARE DATASET USING SILHOUETTE SCORE VALUE

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ABSTRACT

The huge amount of healthcare data, coupled with the need for data analysis tools has made data mining interesting research areas. Data mining tools and techniques help to discover and understand hidden patterns in a dataset which may not be possible by mainly visualization of the data. Selecting appropriate clustering method and optimal number of clusters in healthcare data can be confusing and difficult most times. Presently, a large number of clustering algorithms are available for clustering healthcare data, but it is very difficult for people with little knowledge of data mining to choose suitable clustering algorithms. This paper aims to analyze clustering techniques using healthcare dataset, in order to determine suitable algorithms which can bring the optimized group clusters. Performances of two clustering algorithms (Kmeans and DBSCAN) were compared using Silhouette score values. Firstly, we analyzed K-means algorithm using different number of clusters (K) and different distance metrics. Secondly, we analyzed DBSCAN algorithm using different minimum number of points required to form a cluster (minPts) and different distance metrics. The experimental result indicates that both K-means and DBSCAN algorithms have strong intra-cluster cohesion and inter-cluster separation. Based on the analysis, K-means algorithm performed better compare to DBSCAN algorithm in terms of clustering accuracy and execution time.

KEYWORDS

Dataset, Clustering, Healthcare data, Silhouette score value, K-means, DBSCAN

For More Details : <https://airconline.com/ijcsit/V10N2/10218ijcsit03.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit2018_curr.html

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